

5G META

D7.2

5G META Website and other communication materials

www.5gmeta-project.eu

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
D	Deliverable (e.g. D7.2)
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
M	Month (e.g. M3)
R&D	Research and Development
SME	Small Medium Enterprise
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

5GMETA's website <https://5gmeta-project.eu/> has been designed to represent the project in a complete, transparent and user-friendly manner. The website will be an important dissemination tool for 5GMETA, as it will contain all the necessary information about the project and will be constantly updated with the latest information. It will be the project's main channel to the outside world, providing information about 5GMETA objectives, partners, methodologies, results, publications, news and success stories. The website's design has been carefully selected to follow 5GMETA' brand identity: all visual elements have been created by deconstructing the project's logo and placing its components in the website's space, to create a well recognisable visual pattern while browsing 5GMETA' information. The website includes several dedicated sections in order to be as complete as possible. After its launch at the beginning of M3 (2 November 2020), the website includes information about the project's objectives, the consortium, the use cases, the activities for SMEs and startups, the social media links and the contact details. An acknowledgment to the EU co-funding accompanied by the EU flag is displayed in the footer of each page of the website. Some of the sections, which content will be available at a later stage in 5GMETA' implementation (such as deliverables, presentation, etc.), are going to be hidden, even though they are already part of the website's structure and functionality. These sections are Publications, Presentations, Video gallery and Deliverables. This content will be published as soon as it will be available. The website will be updated on a regular basis and may also be revised as the project progresses. 5GMETA' social media accounts, namely a Twitter hashtag, will actively advance the project's dissemination activities and serve as reflector of the website's content.

1 INTRODUCTION

This deliverable presents information related to D7.1, going in depth with the website and other communication tools. It describes the project's website and its functionality, related to the project's goals and target audience identified in D7.1. It also provides information related to measurements of performance of the website, in relations to the KPIs set in D7.1, as well as for the social media account that was chosen for the project.

1.1 Purpose of the deliverable

This deliverable provides a description of 5GMETA's website and outlines its structure, design and functionalities. It also describes a set of communications material for the promotion of the project.

1.2 Intended audience

This is a public document, and can be consulted by the European Commission, 5GMETA's consortium partners as well as external stakeholders.

1.3 Relation with other work packages/deliverables

This report is complementary to 5GMETA Deliverable 7.1, which presents the project communication and dissemination strategy taking into account the intended audience, stakeholders, dissemination channels and opportunities, appropriate communication tools, etc. Any eventual change in D7.1 that would affect D7.2 would be implemented in the latter. D7.2 deliverable focusses on the website as a tool developed specifically to fulfil the goals of the communication plan, as well as on the communication materials.

2 5GMETA WEBSITE

The 5GMETA project website domain name is www.5gmeta-project.eu. The website will be an important communication and dissemination tool for 5GMETA, as it will contain all the necessary information on the project and will be constantly updated with the latest information. It will be the project's main channel to the outside world, providing information on 5GMETA objectives, partners, methodologies, results, publications, news and success stories. As nowadays a high number of website visits happen via mobile phones, a mobile version of the website is also available.

2.1 Structure and content

5GMETA website's high-level structure has been created to display information about the project in a transparent and accessible manner. It comprises the elements below.

2.1.1 Homepage

The homepage (Figure 1 and 2), being the point of entry for site visitors, presents essential project information and uses a simple layout to place focus on the branding and also to facilitate the navigation. The header area contains the project's logo on the left side and the menu bar on the central-right side. The menu bar has been divided into Home, Objectives, Use Cases, SME & Startup Activities, Consortium, News & Events and Library.

The homepage is laid out as follows:

- It features a visual banner with an image representing a connected world. The image embodies the colours of the project's visual identity. Below the project's name there is a short sentence summarising the project: "Captured-car Data".
- Below, an explanation of 5GMETA, and four images representing the concepts of data privacy, security, interoperability and ownership.
- A "Learn more" button, which redirects the user to the "Objectives" page.
- The same image as the one at the top of the page, with a purple filter, accompanied by the project disclaimer, a Twitter icon edirecting the user to the project's hashtag (#5GMETA) and two contact details: One from the Project Coordinator (VICOMTECH) and one from the Dissemination Manager (ERTICO).
- The home page ends with a footer containing the project's copyright (©2020 5GMETA) and the privacy and cookie policy. This footer is present in each page of the website.

The 5GMETA open platform aims to leverage car-captured data to stimulate, facilitate and feed with them innovative products and services.

Figure 1: 5GMETA's upper home page

Figure 2: SGMETA's lower home page

2.1.2 Objectives

This page provides a more detailed description of the project's main objectives, each one with subpoints, as indicated in Figure 3: Overview of the Objectives page.

Figure 3: Overview of the Objectives page

2.1.3 Use Cases

This page outlines 5GMETA’s three use cases, which will be validated throughout the duration of the project:

- Data-driven Product innovation.
- Data-driven Process innovation.
- Data-driven Business Model innovation spanning.

Each use case is accompanied by a short description, as shown in Figure 4: Use Cases upper page.

5GMETA will be tested and validated for 3 heterogeneous and innovative use cases:

Data-driven Product innovation

This use case includes:

- Product Enhancement: improving or personalising customer experience.
- Product Augmentation: creating a digital ecosystem around connected car sensors data with an accompanying cloud.
- Data as a Product: analysing values to retrieve actionable information for advertising, location-based services, recommendation systems and predictions.

Data-driven Process innovation

This use case includes:

- Enterprise Process Innovation: optimising internal R&D processes from feedback/field operations datasets and alleviating costs.
- Customer Process Innovation: optimising direct impact on customer experience through timely and personalized communications.

Data-driven Business Model innovation spanning

This use case includes:

- Value Model Innovation: provide new methods of value generation for the customer.
- Monetisation Model Innovation: offer innovative ways of value recording for the company.

Figure 4: Use Cases upper page

Scrolling down the page, the user will find three boxes, each one comprised of a description and image. These boxes contain in-depth information about each one of the three use cases, namely “R&D Live Training Loop”, “Use Case Networking Parking” and “Use Case Driving Safety & Awareness”. By clicking one each of these boxes, the user can read more information about the use case and learn from practical examples where these use cases can take place, as well as the specific 5G enabled scenario, as illustrated in Figure 5 and 6.

Figure 5: Overview of the three Use Cases

R&D Live Training Loop

Enabling real time messaging of raw sensor data and data processing with 5G.

5G enables online sensor data sharing from car fleets to a central server. This optimizes the traditional R&D pipeline used in Autonomous Driving, based essentially on collecting datasets, training neural machine learning models and testing those neural models against datasets. This pipeline is run in loop until satisfactory results are obtained. Currently, the datasets are stored locally in the car and then moved to the laboratory in a hard disk. TIER1 and OEM car fleets are geographically distributed across all the continent, so the process can get quite slow. However, 5G enables sending the raw sensor data to a central server in real time. Not only this, models can be updated both in the cloud and in the car on demand, improving significantly the current process. This process optimization can reduce the already quite high R&D costs of CAAM. The technical innovation can also be used for other purposes such as forensic analysis to clarify product liability.

Example

Before a new vehicle, an autonomous driving or a mobility system enters mass production, an OEM or a Tier1 performs field tests of their technologies. The Training Loop produced by the OEM or Tier1's R&D department delivers different versions to monitor driving dynamics, road conditions and system performance, but to optimize such system, new datasets are required to progress in the model train, test and update loop. When it comes to car-captured data, the volume is so high that storing that data in the vehicle for a later batch processing makes the process slow and complicated, however, 5G enables live messaging of raw sensor data for real-time processing and over-the-air software and models updates. The live and remote monitoring of the car systems allows real-time analysis and diagnosis to identify unsafe conditions and expand datasets from the different dynamics captured by on-board sensors and cameras according to the driving dynamics. Thus, R&D departments can optimize the new features and functions from data coming through a real-time pipeline.

5G enabled scenario

This use case needs the 5G v16.0 feature as the cars need to continuously upload data to the cloud service which analyse new data to detect unsafe conditions and trigger training processing to update machine learning/artificial intelligence/computer vision models to send a new update to all the testing fleet, it's

3
Years operating

11
Partners

4
European Countries

Figure 6: Specific overview of one of the three Use Cases

2.1.4 SME & Startup Activities

Because 5GMETA will be involving SMEs and startups in its activities, a dedicated page has been built. The “SME & Startup Activities” page includes important information about 5GMETA’s plan and intended involvement with such reaties and provides six reasons to join. An overview of this page is represented in Figure 7: SME & Startup Activities page.

Be the new automotive player in the 5G ecosystem!

Are you a SME or start-up? Then you too can get involved in 5GMETA! The project will organise a series of hackathons and events where new business opportunities can be created for you.

Tell me more!

With connected and automated mobility applications expanding at fast pace, the value of data from vehicles is vital not only for the automotive industry, but also for new players such as SMEs and high-tech start-ups. That's why 5GMETA will support and train the teams attending hackathons to involve them in its functional prototypes of services and applications. The 5GMETA platform will be used as a basis to create new solutions, assuring interoperability that could either evolve from the current 5GMETA use cases or be created from scratch.

Reasons to join

- Vendors will have the chance to run interoperability test sessions using test descriptions provided in approved guidelines..
- The events will include debriefing sessions where experts can answer technical

Figure 7: SME & Startup Activities page

2.1.5 Consortium

This section offers quick access to information about the project partners (Figure 8: Consortium page). It contains the description, logo and link to the website of each partner of the project consortium. The content was drafted in collaboration with each partner, following a specific scheme, which guarantees consistency throughout all descriptions.

Figure 8: Consortium page

2.1.6 News & Events

This page is divided into news at the top (Figure 9: News) and events at the bottom (Figure 10: Events). Both sections show the latest three items published. By clicking on “See more news” and “See more events”, visitors can view older entries. The news posting will follow specific criteria, such as: news about project status, reference to events, information about 5G related news etc.

Figure 9: News page

Figure 10: Events page

2.1.7 Library

When visiting the Library page, the visitor may access a variety of material, in the following order: deliverables, presentations, publications, articles mentioning 5GMETA (this section is called “In the media”), videos and photos (this section is called “Photo Gallery”).

Many documents (the public deliverables, the presentations and publications) in this page will be also available for download by the consortium and any interested website visitor.

Until the project has developed content to fill each section, ERTICO will proceed with unpublishing empty sections.

Figure 11: Library page

3 PRIVACY POLICY

5GMETA’s website will be compliant with the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). To fulfil the requirements set by this Regulation, 5GMETA’s website will implement a cookie policy specific for the website and link the privacy policy to ERTICO’s corporate website <https://ertico.com/>, as ERTICO will be the one accessing all data (especially for Google Analytics).

4 TECHNICAL ASPECTS

5GMETA’s website has been built with WordPress, using the latest theme available: Divi. This theme allows the website manager to add, remove and change items directly from the front-end of the website. The performance of the website will be tracked using Google Analytics (Figure 12). The parameters chosen to track such performance are the number of visitors and the location from where they visit 5GMETA’s website. Such parameters will provide a useful insight into the project’s communication activities, as it will reflect the outreach of the project’s communication activities.

Figure 12: 5GMETA Google Analytics

5 WEBSITE KPI

KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) are a measurable value that demonstrates how effectively a company, organisation, or in this case a project, is achieving key objectives. As outlined in the section “KPIs” of the public deliverable D7.1 (Table 3), 5GMETA is expected to reach 100 visitors per month in year 1 of the project’s life span, and 150 visitors per month within year 2. In terms of news items, these shall be published on 5GMETA’s website and be 10 or more within year 1 of the project, and 15 or more within the third year. Scientific publications will also be present on the website. The target number set for the first year is of 2 or more publications and 8 or more citations.

With the Google Analytics tool, 5GMETA will be able to measure its performance in terms of number of visitors of its website (including new visitors), the time spent visiting the website, the top pages visited, the country from which users accessed the website, the language used and the tool from which the search was conducted (computer, smartphone or tablet).

6 OTHER COMMUNICATION MEANS AND MATERIALS

On top of the website, 5GMETA will produce a series of communication materials throughout the lifespan of the project, namely:

- Social media channels.
- Videos.
- Brochures, fliers and posters.

Each material will be explained in detail below.

6.1 Social media

Social media will be used to expand the outreach of the project in a more general, modern and immediate way. Posts with information and visualisation of data will be created to engage the digital audience. Social media will be used, especially Twitter and LinkedIn for different messaging.

6.1.1 Twitter

The project will not create its own Twitter account, which would give a disadvantage as it would have to start from scratch, but will use the well established accounts of previous activities and partners.

5GMETA's consortium has agreed to use a hashtag for the project: #5GMETA. This hashtag has not been used for any other EU-funded project or general activity, providing a unique reference to the project. The performance of the hashtag will be monitored in two ways: via Twitter insights and ERTICO's Meltwater platform¹.

¹ Meltwater is a media monitoring platform purchased by ERTICO. Thanks to this platform, ERTICO can schedule and monitor the performance of various media tools, including social media.

Figure 13: Example of 5GMETA's Twitter feed

6.1.2 LinkedIn

The project will not create its own LinkedIn company page or group, which would give a disadvantage as it would have to start collecting followers or members from scratch. Instead, the project will rely on the hashtag #5GMETA and on the well established accounts of existing 5G groups, as well as on the project partners' company pages. A LinkedIn group or company page could be opened later during the project's life span, to foster the exchange of information towards other identified groups. A preliminary list of LinkedIn groups has already been identified in Table 1. This list will be updated as the project progresses. Consortium members will identify relevant groups where 5GMETA related information can be published, widening the outreach opportunities.

LinkedIn group	Link to group
5G Technology	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/6788636/
LTE & 5G Security	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/4029600/
Intelligent Mobility	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/8382671/
5G The NanoCore	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/3686522/
Intelligent Transport	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/3273806/

Table 1: 5GMETA LinkedIn groups

5GMETA has already started being promote on LinkedIn. Tracking on LinkedIn is possible thanks to the hashtag #5GMETA.

Figure 14: Example of posts related to 5GMETA on LinkedIn

6.2 Videos

In-house videos will be made according to the availability of the resources. Where possible, ERTICO will film and edit non-professional videos, including interviews for the website. The videos should depict the project advancements and progresses and distributed online.

Partners are encouraged to produce short videos showing the project services and usage as well as further distribute the webcasts produced by ERTICO.

The project will not create its own YouTube channel, which would give a disadvantage as it would have to start collecting followers from scratch and as the project would not be producing a high amount of videos suitable for a YouTube channel. Instead, the project will rely on [ERTICO's existing YouTube channel](#), and stored in a dedicated playlist, as this has already been done for various European-funded projects.

Figure 15: ERTICO's YouTube channel

6.3 Printed material

Fliers, brochures and a roll-up may be produced for the project, especially in occasion of events. With 5GMETA having started during the COVID-19 pandemic, the production of such material might be postponed until physical events restart. The creation of an interim flier may be foreseen to meet the needs of consortium partners participating at virtual events (e.g. Virtual ITS European Congress 2020).

6.4 Images and photographs

Some professional photographs might be purchased for the promotion of the project, if the budget allows and it is claimed necessary. At important events and milestones, a professional photographer could be hired to take pictures of events and demos.

The images will be used for internal and external dissemination and communication materials, such as presentations, brochures, articles etc. If the images are copyrighted, the source has to be mentioned. With the creation of 5GMETA's website, an image bank has been created and made available to the consortium on the collaborative platform established for the project on Microsoft Teams for download and use related to the promotion of the project.

Should valuable photos be produced for the project, the consortium might be encouraged to upload and share them on their social media platforms (e.g. Flickr).

6.5 Acknowledgment of EU funding

As the project is co-funded by the European Union, communication and publication materials should clearly acknowledge receipt of EU funding through the display of the EU flag and/or the mention:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 957360.”

7 CONCLUSIONS

5GMETA's website was delivered at the beginning of month 3 of the project's lifespan. The website fully embeds the visual identity set at the beginning of the project and it is built following a structure that best contains and communicates the project's resources and findings. In conclusion, the current website represents a good and efficient starting point on which the project can progress and build itself, and will be constantly updated as 5GMETA progresses.

8 REFERENCES

1. Sara Jane Weeks (2020). D7.1 Dissemination & communications strategy.

